

FUNCTIONS OF PARALINGUISTIC MEANS

Abduazizova Durdona Abduzukurivna

DSc., assist. professor of Tashkent institute

E-mail: jemchujina1970@mail.ru

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Annotation

The article considers the functions of paralinguistic means in written and oral speech. The use of paralinguistic means is very diverse and is used in all speech acts, both in oral and written communication. In the structure of the utterance, paralinguistic means act as paraphonational and parakinetic means. The author analyzes excerpts of works by foreign writers and makes an argument about the polyfunctionality of paralinguistic means.

Keywords: linguistic and paralinguistic means, paraphonetic and parakinetic means, polyfunctionality, emotivity, expressivity, functionality.

The main task of communication is to strive for a correct and complete understanding of communicants. In order to adequately convey his thought, a person uses various means offered by language, as well as non-verbal means. The language does not always have enough linguistic expressive means to fully convey the content invested in them. As the researchers note, “these tools in any language are more or less limited, incomplete and insufficiently perfect. Language very often expresses something approximately, it is forced to go to its goal in complex and roundabout ways” [4, c.91]

A large branch of science that studies the transmission of information in a non-verbal way is called paralinguistics. Paralinguistics, which studies nonverbal components, is divided into three types:

- a) paraphonetic (various types of filling pauses, tempo of speech, timbre, volume, melodization, etc.), specific speech sounds (ethical, social and dialect);
 - b) parakinetic (gestures, facial expressions, gestures, posture, etc.);
 - c) graphic (punctuation marks, handwriting, graphic additions, symbols such as §, & etc.).
- These tools are called the term “paragram”. [3, c. 367]

Despite a significant number of works devoted to the study of paralinguistic phenomena, many issues related to the problems of socio-cultural, pragmatic, cognitive factors determining the functional essence of paralinguistic phenomena remain insufficiently developed.

The actual problem of paralinguistics is the problem of functional conditionality of paralinguistic means. Functionality is the main parameter, the essential feature of paralinguistic tools.

Currently, the attention of linguists is mainly focused on the study of the functional aspect of paralinguistic means. However, the functions associated with the expression of various emotions are mainly noted. In recent years, studies have appeared on the comparative nature and functioning of non-verbal means in German, English, Chinese, Korean, Tatar, Kazakh languages (M. Kurbanov, I. Kreidlin, O.V. Mudraya, N.V. Dutova, etc.); issues of verbal and non-verbal transmission of emotions in different linguistic cultures (E.Y. Mirtskhulava, M.D. Gorodnikova, etc.); national and cultural specifics of paralinguistic means A.F. Losev, P.A. Florensky, A. Gehlen, N.A. Bernstein, M. Moss, etc.).

A review of the linguistic literature on this issue has shown that the following functions of paralinguistic means are mainly considered:

- a) expressive, aimed at enhancing the expressiveness of speech;
- b) emotional, aimed at expressing various emotions and describing the inner emotional state of the communicant;
- c) the function of characterizing communicants in terms of their age, gender, social characteristics, cultural, educational, and professional level.

Paralinguistics, as the science of nonverbal communication, is characterized by various approaches to the analysis of paralinguistic means.

In fiction, especially in the speech of the characters, the paralinguistic means that are used in various communication situations are most clearly reflected. Considering parophonetics, it is necessary to focus on the concept of "phonation". Phonation, in general, is defined as a physiological phenomenon associated with the properties of the human vocal apparatus. Phonation signs such as timbre, voice strength, overtones, diction, etc. are noted. It is important to keep in mind that certain phonation signs can, on the one hand, characterize the physiological properties of a person (innate features of timbre, diction, speech defects, etc.), on the other – the properties of a person's voice caused by his internal psychological state, for example, voice volume, gnashing of teeth, whispering, etc. Only in the second case, in our opinion, phonation signs can be considered as paralinguistic means, since they carry a certain semantic and functional load

Ernest Hemingway's short story "The First Forty-nine" contains words of a paralinguistic nature:

"Finish your breakfast and we'll be starting."

"It's not light yet," she said. "This is a ridiculous hour."

Just then the lion roared in a deep-chested moaning, suddenly guttural, ascending vibration that seemed to shake the air and ended in a sigh and a heavy, deep-chested grunt.

"He sounds almost here," Macomber's wife said.

"My God," said Macomber. "I hate that damned noise."

"It's very impressive."

"Impressive. It's frightful." [6, p.74]

In this passage, the phenomena of phonation are materialized by the following lexical units: *"roared, in a deep-chested moaning, suddenly guttural, ascending vibration that seemed to shake the air and ended in a sigh and a heavy, deep-chested grunt."* The author conveys phonation signs, describing and characterizing the moan of a lion, expressed in the following units: «*deep-chested moaning*», suddenly guttural with an upward vibration that seemed to shake the air and ended with a sigh and a heavy, deep chest grunt.

In this example, a detailed description of the phonational features of a roaring lion fulfills the function of emotional impact on a person and characterization of the character's internal psychological state, feelings of anxiety, nervousness and fear experienced by him, which is confirmed by the linguistic context (*damned noise, impressive, frightful.*)

There is an opinion that there is a distinction between "paralinguistic means" and "phonational signs" depending on the functions they perform. J.Catford distinguishes "paraphonological, non-phonological and phonological" functions within "phonational signs". [1, p.26]

From this point of view, "paraphonological functions" mean those phonation differences that are directly correlated with contextual differences: an example is the difference between a voice and a whisper. The voice belongs to the natural, i.e. unmarked, context, and the whisper belongs to the so-called conspiratorial context.

By non-phonological functions, J. Catford understands "those phonational signs, the differences of which are directly related to the situation to characterize individual speaking in a language or dialect, while phonational differences characterize gender, age, health, etc., but they are not contrasting in a linguistic sense". [1, p.30]

Paralinguistic means, which primarily include gestures and facial expressions, are characterized, as already noted, by functional significance, which is the most important parameter determining the essence of paralinguistic phenomena.

Let's turn to the work of A. Cronin "Three loves":

"Her gaze, shielded against the glare, travelling across the road to Bowie's boatyard, picked up the figure of her son playing aboard the Eagle, helping or hindering Dave as he worked on the deck of the tiny launch moored to the grey-stone slip. More likely hindering, she thought, severely stifling all maternal fondness.

Half smiling to herself, she turned and paused before the oak wardrobe, now

confronting her image in the glass with the natural instinctive seriousness of a woman before a mirror...

*She raised a hand to her dark brown hair, regarded herself only for a moment, then, folding the plain cotton dress she had worn during the day, she placed it in the bottom drawer of the wardrobe and, **making a last swift inspection** of the room to ensure its order, noting the shining linoleum, the exactitude of the antimacassar upon the fluted rocker, the smooth hang of the white bed-mat, **she gave a neat movement of satisfaction with her head, swung round, and went downstairs...**" [2, p.58]*

In this passage, the gestures and facial expressions of the hero are expressed by such linguistic means as «*gaze, shielded against the glare travelling across the road*»), *half smiling, to herself, she turned and paused, raised a hand to her dark brown hair, regarded herself only for a moment, gave a neat movement of satisfaction with her head, swung round, and went downstairs*".

The use of these paralinguistic tools performs several functions in this text fragment: 1) achieving the authenticity of the described situation through a detailed and consistent enumeration of all the movements, gestures and facial expressions of the character;

2) characterization of the character as a true woman ("considering his reflection with seriousness", "taking a cursory glance around the room") 3) expressions of the inner state of mind ("smiling", "throwing with satisfaction").

It should be noted that in fiction, especially in the speech of characters, the paralinguistic means that are used in various communication situations are most clearly reflected, forming the so-called "paralinguistic context".

Paralinguistic means can express the psychophysiological state of a person. For example, in Jack London's work "A Daughter of the Snows" phonation signs are used, i.e. exclamations, prolongation and strength of vowel sounds, shouting in the act of communication, narrowing and expanding the range of voice when transmitting information, pauses and their duration, raising and lowering the basic tone of voice, etc. Some of them are presented in the following a fragment.

«Jove! » - he muttered, doffing his cap gallantly. «There is a woman! » And a sudden hunger seized him, and a yearning to see himself mirrored always in the gray eyes of Frona Welse. He was not analytical; he did not know why; but he knew that with her he could travel to the end of the earth. He felt a distaste for his profession, and a temptation to throw it all over and strike out for the Klondike whither she was going; then he glanced up the beetling side of the ship, saw the red face of Thad Ferguson, and forgot the dream he had for an instant dreamed.

Splash! A handful of water from his strenuous oar struck her full in the face. "Hope you don't mind it, miss," he apologized. "I'm doin' the best I know how, which ain't much."

"So, it seems», she answered, good-naturedly". [5, p.116]

This passage reveals the feelings and state of the hero, which are expressed in the text by many linguistic and paralinguistic means (exclamation marks, pauses, expressed ellipses and lexical units). Expression «*doffing his cap gallantly*» characterizes the character's manner of behavior, his gallantry. Exclamations (*Love! There is a woman!*) convey a sense of admiration for a woman, and the pause expressed with the help of an ellipsis indicates some confusion and a sense of timidity experienced by the character. Adverb "*good-naturally*" is also a paralinguistic marker, as it indicates the character's complacent tone. It should be emphasized that the functions of characterization of characters, their emotional state in this example, as in many others, are carried out in close interaction of linguistic and paralinguistic means.

It follows from this that the means accompanying communication, and thanks to which communication becomes more effective, including paralinguistic means expressing the psychological state of communicants, are included in the framework of the study of paralinguistics.

The use of paralinguistic means is very diverse and is used in all speech acts, both in oral and written communication. In the structure of the utterance, paralinguistic means act as non-verbal phonational and kinesic means.

The analysis of our material indicates that the functional significance of paralinguistic means is not limited to the emotive function. The unity of the form and content of an utterance is achieved, in addition to purely linguistic means, also by paralinguistic means, which are superimposed on linguistic expressions and perform various functions aimed at expressing various psychological and emotional states of a person, as well as characterizing a linguistic personality in terms of its age, gender, and social characteristics. The most important parameter of paralinguistic tools is their functional orientation, manifested in their multifunctionality in the process of speech communication.

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